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**MetaFora: a bioinformatic pipeline for
characterization of organisms from the new generation
metagenomics**

- Trabajo Fin de Máster -

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Abstract

- *Motivation:* The large amount of data that NGS platforms are generating allows research groups to accumulate a vast amount of information that needs to be processed. In metagenomics, due to the number of different analytical steps needed to process samples, it is necessary to develop pipelines that facilitate or improve such treatment.
- *Results:* In this study, we use soil samples to design and test a comprehensive pipeline for taxonomic and diversity profiling of metagenomic samples that includes all steps from processing and quality control of data generated by next-generation sequencing technologies, to statistical analyses and data visualization.
- *Availability and Implementation:* Brief manual and scripts in Perl are freely available at: <https://github.com/Irvilma/MetaFora>

Introduction

The microbiome term comprises all of the genetic material within a microbiota, that is, the entire collection of microorganisms in a specific niche. More specifically, soil microbiome describes all microorganisms that can be found in soil, including archaea, bacteria, viruses, fungi, protists and other microbial eukaryotes (Fierer, 2017). Soil microorganisms are a key component of ecosystems because of a little amount of soil can contain thousands of microbial taxa. Recent advances in marker gene, genomic and metagenomic analyses have greatly improved the techniques to characterize the soil microbiome.

The direct genetic analysis of genomes found in an environmental sample is known as metagenomics (Thomas, et al., 2012). The idea of isolate and cloning DNA directly from environmental samples was first proposed by Pace (1985), however it was not until 1998 when Handelsman, et al. (1998) first coined the term metagenomics (Mardanov, et al., 2018). The application of modern genomic techniques to the study of communities of microbial organisms directly in their natural environments has avoided the need to isolate and lab cultivation of individual species (Chen and Pachter, 2005). The first studies discovered many thousands of new gene sequences that helped to reveal a large number of taxa that shaped the unexpected complexity of microbial communities (Dröge and McHardy, 2012). Microorganisms are present everywhere in nature and communities of microbes succeed in diverse environments from the human gut (Methé, et al., 2012) to soil, ecosystems or aquatic resources. Analysis of any community is limited by sequencing technology and the availability of reference genomes. The explosion of next-generation sequencing has allowed the sequencing of individual genomes and has begun a revolution in metagenomics and its analysis (Scholz, et al., 2012). The strict sense of the definition of metagenomics -sequencing whole genome of the species found in an environment- could exclude analysis of only a particular gene. However, these analyses are often used along with “strict metagenomic” analysis to complement it, due to the reliable information that it provides.

The main objective of a metagenomic project consists of characterization of a microbial community both taxonomic composition and potential metabolic contribution to the environment. Metagenomic studies can be addressed by two different approaches:

functional and sequence-based metagenomics. The first approach evaluates biochemical and metabolic activities. It is successfully applied for identifying antibiotics, hydrolytic enzymes, antibiotic resistance genes and many others functions. Besides, this methodology allows the characterization of genes encoding enzymes with a particular activity, consequently can identify novel sequences no similarity to the ones already known (Ferrer, et al., 2007; Handelsman, 2004). On the other hand, the sequence-based metagenomics involves high-throughput sequencing of the total environmental DNA, gene search and functional annotation based on homology to known sequences. This method provides information about all potential activities present in the microbial community, nevertheless, this information depends on the existing of gene annotations. Still, the huge amount of information provides by high-throughput techniques accumulate large new data in genetic databases that facilitate and promote the use of this approach to search functional activities of interest (Mardanov, et al., 2018).

Recently, several sequence-based methods have been extensively used: 1) Shotgun sequencing metagenomics reconstruct large fragments or even complete genomes from organisms in a community without previous isolation, allowing the characterization of a large number of coding and non-coding sequences (Escobar-Zepeda, et al., 2015). This method is able to detect several microbes in environmental samples that would go unnoticed in culturing techniques (Neelakanta and Sultana, 2013). 2) Amplicon sequencing is the most widely used method for characterizing the microbiota diversity. In this method, informative marker regions of the genomes from communities are amplified using taxonomical primer targets such as 16S rRNA gene for prokaryotes and 18S rRNA gene or intergenic transcribed spacers (ITS) for eukaryotes (Dröge and McHardy, 2012; Escobar-Zepeda, et al., 2015). The community taxonomic structure is determined by genetic profiling based on 16S rRNA genes. Taxonomic identification is performed via similarity searches against reference 16S RNA database which contains 16S rDNA sequences from identified microorganisms, but it is probably that do not include all sequences found in a sample, that is, could be problematic to identify microbial communities including novel groups or phylogenetically distant from the characterized species (Mardanov, et al., 2018).

The soil samples are extensively used for investigating cause is probably the most complex and heterogeneous microbial habitat on earth. The diversity of soil microbial communities exceeds that of other environments. There are studies focus on

inferring the ecological attributes of undescribed soil microbial taxa from the advance of genomic, metagenomic and marker gene data (Fierer, 2017). Other studies help in understanding other aspects of the soil microbiome as how the increases in nitrogen availability affect the structure and functional characteristics of soil microbial communities (Fierer, et al., 2011). These studies highlight the importance of obtaining a proper taxonomic composition, credible diversity and functionality of a community from metagenomics studies.

In this work, we describe MetaFora, a bioinformatic workflow for analysing soil metagenomic data based on 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing obtained from the application of next-generation sequencing (NGS) platforms.

2. Methods

2.1. Metagenomic data

The data used are fifty soil samples of the amplified 16S rRNA whole gene. They are demultiplexed data (they do not have barcode and primer sequences) and pair-end reads, that is the forward and reverse reads are stored in two separate fastq files. We do not have any metadata of these data.

2.2. Requirements

The pipeline starts working with demultiplexed data. To accomplish the objectives of each step of this pipeline, various programs available for free are needed. The main software and versions are: Qiime1.9.1 (Caporaso, et al., 2010; Kuczynski, et al., 2012), FastQC (Andrews, 2010), Trimmomatic (Bolger, et al., 2014), PEAR (Zhang, et al., 2013) and R (Team, 2000).

2.3. Quality control, editing and merge software

Before analysing sequences from high throughput platforms, a quality control should be performed to ensure that the data are good enough and there are no biases that may affect the result of the analyses. In this pipeline, the quality control is performed using FastQC version 0.11.7, the most used quality assessment tool for evaluating reads (<https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>). The software, written in Java, exports quality report results to an HTML version for each file. This HTML file

contains a document with all graphs embedded into it, in a single file. Moreover, a zip file with the same name that HTML file is created, in which the graphs from the report are presented as separated files. These files contain information of basic statistic, base sequence quality, sequences quality scores, base sequence content, GC content, overrepresented sequences and others.

After that, sequences are edited utilizing Trimmomatic version 0.36, a software that include a variety of processing steps such as: read trimming, identification of adapter sequences and quality filtering (Bolger, et al., 2014). The input and working of the software varies depending on the types of data, single or pair-ends reads (<http://www.usadellab.org/cms/?page=trimmomatic>).

The merge of pair-ends reads is performed with PEAR version 0.9.11. PEAR, implemented in C, is a fast, memory-efficient and accurate merger. It evaluates all possible paired-end read overlaps and implements a statistical test for minimizing the false-positive results. PEAR returns the merged fragment (Zhang, et al., 2013).

2.4. Metagenomic analysis.

QIIME (Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology) is an open-source pipeline (<http://qiime.org>) that allows analysis of high-throughput community sequencing data. QIIME supports a wide range of microbial community analyses and visualizations including network analysis, taxonomic analysis, histograms of within- or between-sample diversity and others. Its modular implementation facilitates the integration and comparison of these diverse analyses (Caporaso, et al., 2010). QIIME is built to analyze amplicons (targeted genes amplified with PCR). The gene marker analysis begins with the construction of operational taxonomic units (OTUs), that is, cluster of reads that are sufficiently similar to one another (Callahan, et al., 2017).

2.4.1. Metagenomic analysis: Integrated databases in the pipeline.

QIIME assigns high-throughput sequencing reads to taxonomic identities using reference databases. By default, taxonomy is assigned based on the Greengenes taxonomy and reference database (McDonald, et al., 2012; Werner, et al., 2012). This resource offers a consistent multiple-sequence alignment of both archaeal and bacterial 16S small-subunit rRNA genes to facilitate taxonomic placement (DeSantis, et al., 2006). The pipeline also offers the Ribosomal Database Project

(RDP; <http://rdp.cme.msu.edu/>) catalogue, that provides aligned and annotated collection of bacterial and archaeal small subunit rRNA genes (16S), and a collection of fungal large subunit rRNA genes (28S) (Cole, et al., 2014). Besides, the pipeline provides the use of SILVA dataset (from Latin silva, forest, <http://www.arb-silva.de>) that contains a quality checked collection of aligned small (16S/18S, SSU) and large (23S/28S, LSU) subunit rRNA sequences for *Bacteria*, *Archaea* and *Eukarya* domains (Quast, et al., 2013).

2.4.2. Metagenomic analysis: diversity profile

In order to define the diversity of communities, two parameters should be considered: species richness (number of species within a biological community) and species abundance (number of individuals per species). This pipeline computes two metrics for elucidating the diversity of our data: *alpha diversity*, is a metric for calculating diversity within a sample/community, and *beta diversity*, that assess the diversity between a collection of samples.

1. Alpha diversity analyses: The use of statistical estimators is used for calculating quantitatively species diversity. This pipeline calculates several non-parametric estimators, that is, they do not depend on the statistical behaviour of the sample and consider low abundance species (Table1).
2. Beta diversity analyses: There are two types of beta diversity indices, ones those comparing organisms' communities through phylogenetic distance information contained in marker genes, as the Unifrac metrics (Lozupone and Knight, 2005); and the second ones, abundance-type indices, in which the abundance similarity is taken into account. These dissimilarity indices treat individuals equally, not species and are affected by sampling size. Bray-Curtis index (Chao, et al., 2006; Escobar-Zepeda, et al., 2015) is one example of this type of beta diversity index.

2.4.3. Metagenomic analysis: Comparative analysis

1. Abundance analyses: The pipeline calculates the Kruskal-Wallis test, also called the “one-way ANOVA on ranks”. It is a rank-based nonparametric analysis used to test if there are statistically meaningful differences between two or more groups.

2. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (Spearman's rho): This step calculates the correlation between sample groups. Spearman's rho is a nonparametric measure of rank correlation. Raw correlation statistics alone reflect only the degree of association between two sequences of numbers or vectors. Likelihood is assigned to this association via a p-value.

3. Results

The pipeline, written in Perl, integrates two main stages: the pre-processing (including quality control of the sequence) and the quantification. The latter consists of three sub-modules: Sub-module I, taxonomy profile, Sub-module II, diversity profile and Sub-module III, comparative integrative analysis.

3.1. Bioinformatics workflow

The complete workflow of the MetaFora pipeline is shown in the Figure 1.

3.1.1 Stage 1: Pre-processing the data

First, users select to analyze single-end (“SE”) or paired-end (“PE”) reads through a flag (-t). Once selected the type of reads, the pipeline performs a quality control to the data using FastQC v0.11.7. After this, reads are edited via Trimmomatic v0.36 for which users select the average quality value of the reads (flag -q) and the value for cutting bases off the end of a read (flag -tr). For more information about these parameters, consult the manual (<http://www.usadellab.org/cms/?page=trimmomatic>). A second quality control employing FastQC v0.11.7 is conducted to test if the sequences have improved after editing. For pair-ends data, the pipeline merges these reads using Pear v0.9.11.

3.1.2. Stage 2: Quantification of the metagenomics data

Quantification stage attempts to elucidate taxonomy structure and diversity profile, in which the alpha and beta diversity and abundance analysis are calculated.

The second stage is performed using QIIME.1.9.1. The quality-filtered sequences of each sample obtained from Stage 1 are pre-processed to generate a single sequence containing information about all samples. This sequence is used at the beginning with all downstream analysis. At this point, several parameters need to be selected, the database for analyzing the data (-db), number of jobs in parallel (-jobs), the name of the mapping file, without extension (-m), the taxonomic level for which the heatmap graphic will be created (-level), and parameters for filtering OTUs table (-sample and -count).

There are three databases available that user can select from a flag (-db): Greengenes 16S rRNA gene (-db "gg"), RDP version 16 (-db "RDP") and SILVA release 128 ("SILVA"). Once the database is selected, the pipeline creates a table including Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) that will be used for taxonomy and diversity profile and comparative analysis.

1. Picking OTUs ("pick_open_reference_otus.py") following the strategy of open reference that QIIME offers. The process runs in parallel (where available) choosing the number of jobs (flags -jobs). This is about assigning similar sequences to Operational Taxonomic Units by clustering sequences based on a similarity threshold and the UCLUST method (Edgar, 2010). The representative sequences of each cluster are used to assign taxonomy using the selected database. The sequences are aligned following the PyNAST (Caporaso, et al., 2009) method and an approximately-maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree based on fasttree method (Price, et al., 2010) is built. Moreover, the step provides a raw OTU table.
2. Identifying ("identify_chimeric_seqs.py") and filtering ("filter_fasta.py", "filter_alignment.py") chimeras: Chimeras are sequences generated due to unequal PCR amplification rates of different 16S rRNA genes that should be removed from the analysis. In this pipeline, the method used to identify Chimeras is vearch v2.9.1 (Rognes, et al., 2016). See <https://github.com/Irvilma/MetaFora> for downloading and installing.
3. Re-building phylogenetic tree ("make_phylogeny.py") and making new OTUs table ("make_otu_table.py") after removing chimeras for downstream analyses.
4. Summarizing sample OTUs count's in which the pipeline creates a stats file (txt) including OTU table information ("biom summarize-table").

3.1.2.1. Submodule I: Taxonomy profile

5. The taxonomy composition analysis: This step includes taxonomy structure summary files and plots by categories calculated from OTU table in which chimeras have been removed. The categories are distributed as: L1 (Kingdom level), L2 (Phylum level), L3 (Class level), L4 (Order level), L5 (Family level), L6 (Genus level) and L7 (Species level).

3.1.2.2. Submodule II: Diversity profile.

6. Alpha diversity: This step consists of generate rarefied OTU tables, compute alpha diversity metrics for each rarefied OTU table and generate alpha rarefaction plots through the script “alpha_rarefaction.py”.
7. Beta diversity: This pipeline performs the script “beta_diversity_through_plots.py” that calculates principal coordinate analysis (PCoA), and creates distances matrixes using Unifrac (based on phylogenetic distance) and Bray-Curtis (based on abundance) metrics. The script return PCoA and distance matrices for each index, that is: Unweighted UniFrac, Weighted UniFrac and Bray-Curtis. Results from PCoA are shown as two- and three-dimensional graphics to be visualized with Emperor (Vázquez-Baeza, et al., 2013) using Google Chrome or other browsers, and the distance matrices are provided as boxplot in a pdf file.

3.1.2.3. Submodule III: Comparative integrative analysis.

8. Abundance analysis: First, the pipeline filters the OTU table using the script “filter_otus_from_otu_table.py” and following two parameters, el minimum number of count for retaining an OTU, and the minimum sample in which the OTU should be present. Both parameters are selected by the users from the terminal (flags `-count` and `-samples`). Once the table is filtered, the pipeline performs two univariate analyses (Kruskal-Wallis test) with the script “group_significance.py”, one test for comparing among all samples and other among categories provided. As the mapping file does not include categories from the metadata, an R script have been included to cluster the samples from the distance matrices obtained in the previous step. This script use “dplyr” (Wickham, et al., 2018) and “purrr” (Henry and Wickham, 2018) R packages.

After creating groups among samples, the R script incorporates this information to mapping file as a new column called “Group”. The R script generates three new mapping file, one for each distance matrix: `mapp_cluster_unweighted_unifrac`, `mapp_cluster_weighted_unifrac` and `mapp_cluster_bray-curtis`. The Kruskal-Wallis test among groups (clusters) is carried out employing the `mapp_cluster_weighted_unifrac`.

9. Visualization: Also, the filtered OTUs table can be visualized as heatmap (“`make_otu_heatmap.py`” does not take into account categories). The graphic representation of the samples, grouped in the categories through interaction networks from the filtered OUT table, is provided by the script “`make_otu_network.py`”. It generates network files to be passed into Cytoscape software (Shannon, et al., 2003). Consult the tutorial for making Cytoscape networks (http://qiime.org/tutorials/making_cytoscape_networks.html). From these filtered OUT table created for the abundance analysis, a new approximately-maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree is built using QIIME1.9.1 that can be visualized in FigTree v1.4 (Rambaut, 2012)
10. Spearman's rho: The pipeline uses the script “`observation_metadata_correlation.py`” for calculation correlation among samples and clusters. The correlation among clusters uses the groups resulted from the weighted Unifrac matrix.

3.2. Case of study: analyzing 16S rRNA metagenomics data.

MetaFora pipeline has been tested using a fifty soil samples in which the 16S rRNA region has been amplified. The data are demultiplexed.

Stage 1: Pre-processing data.

Once the paired-ends reads have been selected (-t “PE”), the pipeline yields a first quality control report using FastQC. These paired-ends reads are edited following the next parameters: -q 20, that drops the read if the average quality is below 20, and -tr 20 that remove low-quality bases from the end when the quality is below 20. After this, a second quality control is completed (Table 2). The FastQC results show quality control reports in which the sequences from the fifty samples slightly improve (Fig. 2). The last

step of this stage consists of merge the paired-end reads using Pear software following the parameters by default.

Stage 2: Quantification.

The second stage has been completed using the three different database provide by the pipeline. The parameters selected are: -db gg (RDP or SILVA), -m mapping_file -level L2 -count 2 -samples 25. The analysis was carried out using Greengenes (RDP and SILVA) database, L2 was the level taxonomic for extracting a heatmap of taxonomy (Phylum level), and the final filtered OTU table used for abundance analysis exclude singleton OTUs and retain OTUs that are present in 25 samples (50%). The results are shown below.

The pipeline offers a summary of the information in the OTU table creating a table (Table 3) that shows general information summary, including the number of samples, the number of observations, the total count (i.e., the sum of all values in the table), followed by the per-sample counts detail.

Taxonomic profile

The results are provided as html file in which the taxonomic structure can be visualized at different taxonomic levels. Our results, based on Greengenes database, show the taxonomic structure obtained via bar charts (Fig. 3). The figure presents the principal microorganisms found in the soil samples at the phyla level. All of them belong to Bacteria kingdom. Firmicutes phylum predominates all metagenomic samples (62.8%), following by Bacteroidetes (10.9 %) and Proteobacteria (9.1 %) phyla. Samples with the highest percentages of Firmicutes phylum are P041T2BS (95.5%) and P079T2BS (90.9%). The lower percentage of this phylum is present in P001T1BT sample (4%) in which the dominant phylum is TM7 (86.8%). Also, there is one sample (P050T2BS) that present a high percentage of another phylum, Cyanobacteria phylum (26.2%). Results based on RDP database (Figure S1) show microorganisms belong to Bacteria kingdom. In this case, Firmicutes (62.7%), Bacteroidetes (9.8%) and Proteobacteria (9.1%) are also the predominated phyla. However, samples that present high percentage of Firmicutes phylum are P041T2BS (95.5%) and P044T1BS (93.5%). P001T1BT sample show the lower percentage of this phylum (3.9%), being “Candidatus Saccharibacteria” the dominating phylum (68.8%). P004T1BT also present high

percentage of this last phylum (34%). Here, “Cyanobacteria/Chloroplast” is also present in the same sample that in the Greengenes case, P050T2BS (26.3%). Results, when SILVA database is applied (Figure S2), show also Firmicutes (63.1%) as the most frequent phylum in the soil sample, followed by Bacteroidetes (10.7%) and Proteobacteria (9.2%). P041T2BS (95.5%) and P044T1BS (93.6%) are the samples that present the highest percentage of the Firmicutes phylum, and P001T1BT the lowest. P001T1BT sample shows an 86.86% of Saccaribacteria phylum. P050T2BS is the only sample presents Cyanobacteria phylum (26.30%).

The taxonomic tree based on 16S rRNA gene shows the phylogenetic relationship of filtered OTUs picked in the analysis. The figure (Fig.4) depicts the taxonomic tree generated after removing chimeras and the heatmap of the taxonomic structure at phylum level for each sample based on Greengenes database.

Diversity profile

For each analysis executed, several graphics are obtained from the alpha diversity analysis (observed OTUs, observed species, Shannon, Simpson and Chao1 indexes). Figure 5 presents the Shannon index and observed OTUs results based on Greengene database. With respect to beta diversity analysis, figure 6 depicts a boxplot in which distance among groups is calculated using the weighted distance matrix for each database used. We can observe that distances have been calculated among a different number of groups since samples have been clustered in different number of groups depend on the database used. Figure 7 shows the PCoA results from unweighted unifrac, weighted unifrac and Bray-Curtis metrics among samples and groups provided based on Greengenes database.

4. Discussion

The developed of sequence amplification and NGS technology has allowed the research groups generate gigabases of genetic information at comparatively low cost having a high impact on the biological investigation. One field of research that has increased in the last years is metagenomics. The high size of the data obtained from NGS platforms together with the existence of numerous different tools for each step of the analytical process, make the data challenging to process.

The metagenomics analyses are based on computational tools for extracting useful and reliable information about the microbiome communities under study. There are available several software tools for bioinformatics analysis of these metagenomic data, those that have been developed to elucidate the taxonomy structure of the community - metagenomic pipeline of Galaxy Platform (Kosakovsky Pond, et al., 2009), CLARK (Ounit, et al., 2015) - and those also shed light on the functional composition - mOTUs (Sunagawa, et al., 2013), QIIME (Caporaso, et al., 2010). The most common bioinformatic tasks that a full metagenomic workflow should comprise are (i) sequencing quality control, (ii) metagenomic assembly, (iii) taxonomic analysis, (iv) comparative analysis, and (v) functional annotation. Each of these tasks requires high processing power and depth knowledge of the suitable application of computational methodologies. MetaFora pipeline carries out most of these steps, except functional annotation.

MetaFora is an automated pipeline focus on a set of marker genes in which the data can be analyzed from the raw sequences up to achieve the taxonomy structure, diversity profile and comparative analyses of the community under study, as well as their graphic representations. The pipeline integrates well-established software to its workflow that contributes different objectives as to recover high-quality sequences creating quality control reports, trimming and merge reads, and also software for metagenomic analysis that generates OTU tables including reliable information in whom the taxonomy and diversity profiles of the community study is based on.

In the quantification metagenomic stage, MetaFora only employs the QIIME software, profiting of the advantages that this software can offer and reducing the entry bias to the workflow. The pipeline carries out, step by step, a completed metagenomics analysis compiling numerous scripts from this software. Thereby the pipeline has easy use and incorporates state-of-the-art algorithms optimized for specific analytical tasks. In order to optimize the computational cost of the necessary bioinformatic tasks for a full metagenomics analysis, MetaFora presents parallel processing design for specific steps exploiting multi-processor configuration, reducing the execution time and getting a proper efficiency of performance.

MetaFora is a reliable pipeline that returns credible results due to the established quality of the software included. These softwares have already been widely tested in the field

and also in diverse previous research studies. By integrating several programs into a single workflow, this pipeline requires several software dependencies, and the installation process can become a bit complicated. However, once all the programs and their dependencies are installed, using the pipeline is simple and fast, just by typing a couple of the command lines in the terminal the raw sequences are analyzed. Moreover, this is a flexible pipeline since users can start the analysis at both stages. Quality control (stage 1) provides high-quality sequences that can be used as input to others software. Likewise, users can start directly in the second stage if the data have been previously filtered and edited.

This pipeline offers the possibility to analyse the data with three different databases. The number of observations (Table 3) varies between analyses, being higher when using the Greengenes and SILVA databases than when using RDP. Also, light differences are found among phylogenetic tree obtained from each analysis (Figure S1 and S2). The results of the taxonomic structure found using different databases are very similar among them, at least phylum level. The principal dissimilarity is found in the beta diversity analysis (Figure 6) since depending on the database used, the samples are clustered in a different number of groups. It is an advantage that the pipeline can generate results using different databases to compare and identify which of them provide more and better results.

Despite its limitations, this pipeline is a straightforward method to start with when 16S rRNA data are available. For future implications, the tool might add to the workflow the functional annotation of a microbial community. Thereby, it would provide evidence for further exploration of the community. Also, the pipeline might allow changing more analysis parameters, contributing to reducing the rigid of the results.

The bioinformatic pipeline described in the present study constitutes a useful tool for amplicon sequencing metagenomics (16S rRNA mainly) which is user-friendly and offers reliable results, proper performance and flexible structure.

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TABLES

Table 1. Description of the different estimators calculated in the pipeline.

Estimator	Description
Chao1 richness estimator	Use the number of rare species found in a sample as a proxy of there is possible to find more undiscovered species. Works for abundance data (Colwell and Coddington, 1994; Chao, 1984)
Shannon- Wiener diversity index (H')	An entropy measurement that increases with the number of species in the sample (Shannon, 1948). Shannon-Wiener gives more weight to rare species in a sample
Simpson's index (D)	The simplest non-parametric diversity estimator. It is based on the probability of assigning two independent individuals taken randomly from the community into the same species (Simpson, 1949). Simpson index gives a higher weight to species with more frequency in a sample
Observed OTUs	It calculates the number of distinct OTUs.
Observed species	The count of unique OTUs found in the sample

Table 2. Total number of reads from each sample (raw and processed data)

Sample	Total number of reads	Number of reads after trimming
P001T1BT_S46_R1	118517	116801
P002T1BS_S23_R1	107257	106260
P003T1BT_S54_R1	163315	158985
P004T1BT_S62_R1	208177	203159
P006T1BT_S70_R1	122889	119540
P007T1BS_S31_R1	116626	116265
P040T1BS_S24_R1	84646	84087
P041T2BS_S25_R1	95925	95434
P042T1BS_S40_R1	97720	97291
P043T1BS_S48_R1	156106	155317
P044T1BS_S56_R1	69647	69218
P045T1BS_S64_R1	88268	86901
P046T2BS_S33_R1	102355	101987
P047T1BS_S41_R1	113322	112708
P050T2BS_S72_R1	122559	121606
P056T1BS_S80_R1	118895	118475
P056T2BS_S2_R1	97185	96658
P059T1BS_S88_R1	136374	135683
P075T2BS_S57_R1	122529	122040
P078T2BS_S65_R1	63575	63336
P079T2BS_S73_R1	112505	112034
P090T1BS_S26_R1	78827	78306
P091T1BS_S34_R1	91715	91257
P098T1BS_S42_R1	103267	101981
P099T1BS_S50_R1	97651	96097
P099T2BS_S58_R1	117051	115881
P100T1BS_S66_R1	85646	85114
P101T1BS_S82_R1	128586	127306
P104T2BS_S90_R1	152870	152066
P105T1BS_S4_R1	127517	126856
P106T1BS_S11_R1	77643	77273
P106T2BS_S19_R1	176742	175252
P108T1BS_S27_R1	98152	97390
P110T1BS_S43_R1	104998	104272
P110T2BS_S5_R1	114725	113971
P111T1BS_S51_R1	329976	328344
P111T2BS_S59_R1	188628	187384
P113T1BS_S83_R1	187230	185880
P113T2BS_S91_R1	234475	232936
P114T1BS_S12_R1	113946	113033
P114T2BS_S20_R1	176277	174880
P115T1BS_S28_R1	92510	91843
P115T2BS_S36_R1	116609	116074
P116T1BS_S44_R1	105038	104361
P116T2BS_S52_R1	129611	128825
P117T2BS_S68_R1	45382	44682
P119T1BS_S76_R1	105249	104406
P126T1BS_S69_R1	71800	71517
P129T2BS_S38_R1	147345	146666
P130T1BS_S7_R1	128158	127153

Table 3. Information the OTU table without chimeras based on three different databases (Greengenes, RDP and SILVA).

OTU table- Greengenes	OTU table- RDP	OTU table- SILVA
Num samples: 50 Num observations: 15.912 Total count: 5.849.916 Table density (fraction of non-zero values): 0.085	Num samples: 50 Num observations: 14.845 Total count: 5.851.840 Table density (fraction of non-zero values): 0.076	Num samples: 50 Num observations: 15.428 Total count: 5.853.606 Table density (fraction of non-zero values): 0.092
Counts/sample summary: Min: 36.602,000 Max: 317.221,000 Median: 108.641,000 Mean: 116.998,320 Std. dev.: 45.837,774 Sample Metadata Categories: None provided Observation Metadata Categories: taxonomy	Counts/sample summary: Min: 36.616,000 Max: 317.308,000 Median: 108.680,000 Mean: 117.036,800 Std. dev.: 45.843,951 Sample Metadata Categories: None provided Observation Metadata Categories: taxonomy	Counts/sample summary: Min: 36.608,000 Max: 317.410,000 Median: 108.717,000 Mean: 117.072,120 Std. dev.: 45.857,392 Sample Metadata Categories: None provided Observation Metadata Categories: taxonomy
Counts/sample detail: P117T2BS: 36.602,000 P078T2BS: 61.341,000 P044T1BS: 66.220,000 P126T1BS: 69.043,000 P090T1BS: 74.071,000	Counts/sample detail: P117T2BS: 36.616,000 P078T2BS: 61.351,000 P044T1BS: 66.256,000 P126T1BS: 69.061,000 P090T1BS: 74.098,000	Counts/sample detail: P117T2BS: 36.608,000 P078T2BS: 61.384,000 P044T1BS: 66.270,000 P126T1BS: 69.092,000 P090T1BS: 74.171,000

FIGURES

Figure 1. Schematic of the workflow.

Figure 2. Summary per base sequence quality of one sample obtained before and after editing sequences.

Figure 3. Bar chart depicting the percentage of taxa found applying Greengenes database in each metagenomic sample.

Figure 4. A) Taxonomic tree based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing data obtained using Greengenes database, and B) Heatmap for phylum level

Figure 5. Observed OTUs and Shannon index (alpha diversity) based on Greengenes database.

Figure 6. Boxplot of group distances from weighted unifracs matrix obtained applying different databases.

Figure 7. 2D representation of PCoA results from the unweighted unifrac, weighted and Bray-Curtis index based on Greengenes database. The "Description" title is referred to samples.

Supplementary material

Figure S 1. Taxonomy profile from analysis using RDP database

Figure S 2. Taxonomy profile from analysis using SILVA database